

An open-source platform for simulation and optimization of clean energy technologies

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Abstract

This paper is to describe an open-source code for optimization of clean energy technologies. The model covers the whole chain of energy systems including mainly 6 areas: renewable energies, clean energy conversion technologies, mitigation technologies, intelligent energy uses, energy storage, and sustainability. Originally developed for optimization of renewable water pumping systems for irrigation, the open-source model is written in Matlab® and performs simulation, optimization, and design of hybrid power systems for off-grid and on-grid applications. The model uses genetic algorithm (GA) as optimization technique to find the best mix among power sources, storage systems, and back-up sources to minimize life cycle cost, and renewable power system reliability.

Keywords: Open-source software; optimization; clean energies; genetic algorithm;

1. Introduction

To reach the target of limiting global warming to +2°C by 2100, the global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions need to be reduced by 40-70% by 2050 and the carbon neutrality needs to be reached by the end of the century at the latest [1]. To achieve these goals is fundamental to develop and deploy a range of renewable energy technologies together with policy incentives. Developing renewable energies technologies has been a crucial point in the agenda of several countries. For instance, Europe has started since the beginning of 90's to develop policies aimed at reducing fossil fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions with the aim of promoting the use of renewable energy for electricity, heating and cooling, and transportation.

The rapid development of renewable energies sector has caused an impressive transformation in the energy generation and distribution systems shifting from centralized generating facilities to more distributed generation [2]. This transformation has led to a general increase of integration and interactions between energy sources, electrical and thermal energy storage systems, conversion and transportation techniques.

The high integration level of energy sources, storage, and clean energy technologies results in a complex energy system to simulate, design, and operate. To understand the interactions and synergies of this complex energy system, an integrated modelling approach is required. Nevertheless, the modelling and simulation of energy generation systems is traditionally carried out simulating a single energy system. Thus, the modelling and simulation of complex integrated and distributed energy systems can be considered as an underdeveloped area of research and application. Several commercial tools are available, such as Homer® [3], PVsyst® [4], Polysun® [5], Trnsys® [6] to list the most well-known. There are also several open-source tool available in the market, such as SAM [7], and RETScreen [8]. All the available commercial software show similar limitations: they are not open-source, meaning high cost for the user license, and they are marked by the impossibility to modify, customize and develop the internal modelling codes. Similarly to the commercial software, those open-source software show the impossibility to modify, customize and develop the internal modelling codes by the end-user. Besides this intrinsic inflexibility, few codes offer easy-to-use optimization capabilities, such as Homer. Moreover, most of the commercial and open-source codes available in the market are constrained by a limited amount of energy sources and storage technologies models, and in general clean energy technologies models.

There is thus the need of a tool to simulate and optimize complex integrated energy systems to guarantee low energy costs, high power quality, and maximize at the same time the reliability of

renewables to pursue climate change targets. The open-source code, originally developed for the optimization of photovoltaic (PV) water pumping systems for irrigation [9] and in general off-grid power systems, can represent an answer to the demand for simulation and optimization tools able to handle complex integrated energy systems. This paper provides a first attempt overview of the developed open-source model and its submodules showing two application examples.

2. Open-source code description

In the current version, the developed open-source code is shared among researchers for optimization, simulation, and design of hybrid power systems for off-grid and on-grid applications [10]. The code models clean energy technologies integrated in micro grids or as distributed generation in larger grids. The model is written in Matlab® and uses genetic algorithm (GA) to find the best combination among power source, storage system, and back-up power source to minimize life cycle cost, and maximize profit and power system reliability. Originally, the model included solar photovoltaic (PV), wind turbine, diesel generator and battery bank for off-grid applications, in particular PV water pumping systems for irrigation. The model has been continuously developed and new power sources, power-to-heat conversion technologies, and storage systems models have been integrated. The open-source code can be a key tool for researchers, consultant and decision makers working in the fields of renewable energies, hybrid power system, distributed energy generation and mini/micro grids.

A schematic diagram of the functioning of open-source code is depicted in Fig. 1. The input data (climatic data, technical and economic parameters) are inserted in one input MS Excel® file that is read by Matlab®. The hourly dynamic modelling and operational strategy are the core of the optimization process. Since there can be several operational strategies to run the entire energy system, for instance how to use the surplus of power generated or how to operate the electrical or thermal energy storage, typically the operational strategy is user-defined. The output of the model consist in the Pareto frontier representing the trade-off of the selected objectives (for instance, minimize life cycle costs (LCC), minimizing levelized costs of electricity (LCOE), maximizing the self-sufficiency ratio (SSR), maximizing the self-consumption ratio (SCR), maximizing the loss of load probability (LOLP), maximizing the crop yield or crop revenues in case of renewable irrigation systems, etc.), and the corresponding decisional variables values (for instance, tilt angle, azimuth angle, PV rated capacity, wind turbine rated capacity, wind tower height, battery capacity, etc.). The main model output, Pareto frontiers and related decisional variables values, are printed in an output MS Excel® file.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of the open-source code optimization process.

3. Open-source code modules

In this section are reported some of the main sub-modules. The most updated version of the developed open-source code counts more than ten sub-modules (PV, wind turbine, battery, diesel generator, hydro

turbine, hydro pumped storage, water harvester, heat pump, building, solar thermal collectors, electrolyzer, fuel cells, GHG emissions, etc.), and several operational strategies.

3.1. PV module

The hourly power generated from the PV array P_{PV} (W) is modelled through the following equation, a modified version from Duffie and Beckman [11]:

$$P_{PV} = \eta_{PV,STC} \left[1 + \frac{\mu}{\eta_{PV,STC}} (T_a - T_{STC}) + \frac{\mu}{\eta_{PV,STC}} \frac{9.5}{5.7 + 3.8v} \frac{(NOCT - 20)}{800} (1 - \eta_{PV,STC}) G_{g,t} \right] A_{PV} G_{g,t} \quad (1)$$

where, $\eta_{PV,STC}$ is the efficiency of the PV module at standard test conditions (STC) (%), μ is the temperature coefficient of the output power (%/°C), T_a is the ambient temperature (°C), T_{STC} is the standard test conditions temperature (25°C), v is the wind speed (m/s), $NOCT$ is the nominal operating cell temperature (°C), A_{PV} is the PV array area (m²) related to the array power peak, and $G_{g,t}$ is the global solar radiation on the tilted surface (W/m²).

3.2. Wind turbine

The hourly power output of the wind turbine P_{WT} (W) is given by the following set of equations [12]:

$$P_{WT} = \begin{cases} 0 & (v < v_i \text{ and } v > v_o) \\ \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p v^3 & (v_i \leq v \leq v_r) \\ P_{WT,r} & (v_r \leq v \leq v_o) \\ 0 & (v < v_i \text{ and } v > v_o) \end{cases}$$

where, v_i , v_r and v_o are the cut-in, rated and cut-out characteristic speeds of the wind power curve (m/s), ρ is the air density (1.225 kg/m³), A is the rotor area (m²), C_p is the power coefficient, v is the actual wind speed (m/s), and $P_{WT,r}$ is the wind turbine rated power (kW).

3.3. Battery

The battery model calculates the state of charge of the battery SOC_{bat} (%) according to the following two equations for charging and discharging respectively [13]:

$$SOC_{bat}(t) = SOC_{bat}(t-1) (1 - \sigma_{sd}(t)) + \frac{\left(\left[P_{PV}(t) - \frac{P_{load}(t)}{\eta_{inv}} \right] \eta_c \right)}{BC} \quad (\text{charging}) \quad (3)$$

$$SOC_{bat}(t) = SOC_{bat}(t-1) (1 - \sigma_{sd}(t)) + \frac{\left(\frac{P_{load}(t)}{\eta_{inv}} - P_{PV}(t) \right)}{BC} \quad (\text{discharging}) \quad (4)$$

where, t indicates the time step at which the parameter is calculated (hours), σ_{sd} is the hourly self-discharge rate, E_{load} is the energy consumption (W), η_{inv} is the inverter efficiency (%), BC is the battery capacity (Wh), and η_c is the battery bank efficiency (%).

3.4. Diesel generator

The diesel generator is typically used as back-up power generation in off-grid power systems. The hourly diesel generator consumption C_{DG} (l/Wh) is given by the following equation [14]:

$$C_{DG} = aP_{load} + bP_{DG,r} \quad (5)$$

where a and b are experimental coefficients, and $P_{DG,r}$ is the rated power of the diesel generator (W). The diesel consumption can be penalized adding carbon taxes.

3.1. Grid

The electric grid is simulated as back-up power and as dumped power system for grid connected hybrid PV-wind battery system. The electricity exchanged with the grid is subject to retail electricity price when taken from the grid or incentives when injected into the grid. Similarly to diesel generator, the electricity taken from the grid can be penalized with carbon taxes within the optimization model.

4. Results

This section shows some of the results achievable with the proposed open-source code. The results shown in this section belongs to two different categories: the first is about optimization of off-grid PV-wind-battery hybrid power systems, while the second refer to optimization of a grid connected PV-wind-battery system.

The simulations results of an off-grid PV-wind-battery hybrid power systems, the core part of the optimization process of a hybrid power system, are depicted in Fig. 2. The figure shows the hourly trend of the PV, wind and diesel generator power output, the electric load requirement, and the corresponding state of charge of the battery. The peaks of the battery state of charge correspond to the time periods when the renewables, PV and wind power systems, are producing more than the electric load requirements. In case the battery SOC is at its minimum, here set as 20%, and there is no power generated from the PV and wind systems, the electric load is met by the diesel generator. In this case, the electric load corresponds with the power produced by the diesel generator. The corresponding results of the optimization process are depicted in Fig.3 in the form of a Pareto frontier. The Pareto frontier shows the optimal relationship between LCC and renewables reliability. As it can be seen from the figure, the Pareto front can be divided in two main parts: for renewable reliabilities higher than 8480 hours up to 8760 hours that correspond to the maximum annual reliability, and for renewables reliabilities lower than 8480 hours. In the second part the LCC increase since the power demand is mostly covered by the diesel generator that dramatically affect the operation and maintenance costs of the entire system, in particular due to the fuel consumption, and thus LCC. Assuming renewable reliability equal to 0 hours, the LCC of the system is 530 kUS\$, far higher than a completely reliable system based on renewables and electric storage system, LCC equal to 290 kUS\$. Fig.4 shows the optimization results in terms of Pareto frontier surface between SSR, SCR and LCC for a Swedish grid-connected household equipped with a PV-wind-battery hybrid power system.

Fig. 2: Hourly simulations of a PV-wind-diesel-battery hybrid power system.

Fig.3: Optimization Pareto frontier of an off-grid PV-wind-battery diesel hybrid power system (renewable reliability versus system life cycle costs).

Fig.4: Optimization Pareto frontier of a grid-connected PV-wind-battery hybrid power system (SSR versus SCR and system life cycle costs).

The optimization results show that 5-6 kW_p PV system combined with 10-50 kWh battery are the optimal solutions to be combined with the current 15 kW wind power system and electric load. The optimal PV system and battery capacities allow to achieve high SSR and SCR, around 100% and 50%, respectively.

5. Conclusions and future works

This paper introduces an open-source platform for the simulation and optimization of integrated clean energy technologies. The code can model more than ten clean energy technologies with several operational strategies. Both the simulation and optimization models and operational strategies can be fully customized in Matlab® environment by the end users. The results of the two examples taken into consideration in this paper shows some of the capabilities of the model to handle simulations and optimization of complex integrated energy systems both off- and on-grid. The optimization of the off-grid system shows how it is crucial to take into consideration the LCC in the optimization of hybrid PV-wind-battery diesel power system. The optimization of the grid-connected hybrid power system shows the relationship between system LCC and two performance indicators, SSR and SCR respectively, for a Swedish household. The development of the open-source code will follow two main directions: development of further models to be integrated in the current version, and validation of the models and optimization technique. The validations will be carried out using a grid-connected hybrid power system installed at Mälardalen University (0.9 kW_p PV system, 1 kW wind turbine, and 4 kWh lead acid battery). Further validations will be performed comparing the developed model with other commercial and open-source software.

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Biography

Pietro Elia Campana graduated in Environmental Engineering at the University of Perugia, Italy. He received his PhD in Energy and Environmental Technology at Mälardalen University, Sweden. Currently, he is postdoctoral researcher at Mälardalen University. He is the main coordinator and one of main developers of the open-source code OptiCE (www.optice.net).